

north american
academic research

Review

Review on Anesthetic for Laparoscopic Liver Resection

Mintah Bright Darko^{1*}, Odowa Yusuf Ahmed¹, Cai Xiu Jun¹, Wang Yi Fan¹

¹Department of General Surgery, Sir Run Run Shaw Hospital, Zhejiang University School of Medicine, Hangzhou, China PR

*Corresponding Author :

Mintah Bright Darko

Email: gyptian@msn.com

Published online : 26 April, 2019

Abstract: *We identify the expansive scope of soporific contemplations that influence the result of patients experiencing laparoscopic liver resection. Key components for great results after laparoscopic liver resection are cautious patient choice and hazard stratification, fitting checking, methods to decrease blood misfortune and transfusion, and dynamic recuperation the board. Albeit a portion of these key components are the equivalent for open liver task, there are explicit soporific contemplations of which both the careful and anesthesia groups must know to accomplish ideal patient results after laparoscopic liver resection. While novel focal points of laparoscopic liver resection commonly incorporate diminished intraoperative dying, transfusion necessities, and a lower occurrence of postoperative ascites, explicit difficulties incorporate administration of the confounded interchange between low-volume anesthesia and expanded intraabdominal weight due to pneumoperitoneum, with extra contemplations in regards to circulatory help to treat intense blood misfortune with requirement for new change at times. This article will address in detail the preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative analgesic contemplations for patients experiencing laparoscopic liver resection that both the careful and anesthesia group ought to know about to improve results.*

Keywords: Anesthetic, laparoscopic, liver resection

Introduction

An open liver resection is a noteworthy surgery and generally has been related with a high dreariness and mortality, most regularly brought about by discharge or postoperative liver disappointment (Stümphe et al, 2009). In the course of the most recent thirty years propels in careful and soporific procedures and the executives alongside better patient choice have created a critical decrease in perioperative hazard. Postoperative mortality as of now remains at around 3% (Simmonds et al, 2006): in any case, horribleness stays high, 15---35% (Karanjia et al, 2009; Nordlinger et al, 2008; Parikh et al, 2003). Around 10% of liver resections are required for generous injuries, including hemangiomas, central nodular

hyperplasia and hepatic adenomas. 90% of liver resections are performed for threatening injuries, 20% of which are essential malignancies and 80% metastatic (Stümphe et al, 2009). The most widely recognized essential harm of the liver is hepatocellular carcinoma, representing roughly 80% of cases. The second most normal is cholangiocarcinoma disease emerging from the bile conduit. By a long shot the most widely recognized sign for liver resection is for the evacuation of metastatic stores of colorectal malignant growth. In the UK there are around 32,000 new instances of colorectal malignant growth every year, 20---25% of which will have liver metastases (Stümphe et al, 2009). Those with no proof of inaccessible spread might be appropriate for liver resection medical procedure, which in the UK means around 1600 liver resections for each year (Garden et al, 2006). Liver resection medical procedure remains the main potential solution for these patients and when joined with neoadjuvant chemotherapy, multi year survival can be as high as 46% (Karanjia et al, 2009).

Anatomy and physiology of the liver

As laid out above, verifiably liver resection was related with a high mortality, up to 20% in the 1970's (Stümphe et al, 2009). The main sources of this were huge drain and postoperative hepatic deficiency, which are legitimately identified with the way that the liver is both profoundly vascular and metabolically extremely dynamic playing out various fundamental physiological capacities. The checked decrease in mortality over ongoing years has come to fruition to a limited extent because of a superior comprehension of the life structures and physiology of the liver. The liver has a rich blood supply getting around 30% of resting heart yield (1.5 lites.min---1). 20% of the blood stream comes straightforwardly from the foundational flow by means of the hepatic supply route: the staying 80% originates from the entryway vein which conveys blood depleting from the digestion tracts. Most of venous waste is by three hepatic veins which join the substandard vena cava.

The liver is an expansive organ weighing g and arranged in the correct upper guts. It might be partitioned either dependent on its surface life systems or by means of practical portions. From the surface highlights, there are four flaps partitioned by gaps; the privilege and left projections are front with the littler caudate and quadrate flaps back. There are five tendons associating the liver to the stomach and the stomach divider, the falciform (which additionally separates the privilege and left projections), the coronary, the privilege triangular, the left triangular and the round tendons

With regards to careful resection, it is smarter to separate the liver into its eight utilitarian portions as it has been built up that segmental resections offer indistinguishable advantages from great lobar resections with less hazard than is related with the evacuation of a huge volume of useful liver tissue (Billingsley et al, 1998; Scheele and Stangl, 1994). There are coordinating divisions of entryway vein, hepatic conduit and bile channel providing each portion. This implies adjoining portions can be resected without upsetting the blood supply to the neighboring ones. Bile delivered by the liver from the breakdown of hemoglobin is gathered in bile canaliculi which converge to form bile conduits. These channel into the left and right hepatic conduits which at that point join to shape the regular hepatic pipe.

The metabolic elements of the liver incorporate sugar and lipid digestion, protein amalgamation including coagulation variables and plasma proteins and the digestion of different medications. It additionally assumes a significant job in insusceptible capacity, endocrine capacity and is a site of capacity for some fundamental substances, for example, nutrients and iron. Postoperative hepatic deficiency/disappointment happens when there is deficient useful liver tissue staying following resection. In any case, in spite of its unpredictability the liver is versatile and can keep up satisfactory capacity with up to 66% of its mass expelled. Notwithstanding this the liver can recover following resection. This marvel happens by means of hyperplasia of the leftover cells and implies that progressively broad resections are conceivable whenever led in stages.

Anaesthesia for liver resection surgery

All patients require general anesthesia with endotracheal intubation and controlled ventilation as standard. Patients with liver disappointment may have a bigger volume of circulation for enlistment operators yet their disabled hepatic digestion enhances this impact and the portions of acceptance operator remain basically the equivalent (Servin et al, 1988). Inhalational operators are all the more regularly utilized for support, as they decline liver blood stream more than intravenous specialists, decreasing the danger of dying. Isoflurane is the most regularly utilized of the inhalational operators. Sevoflurane has been appeared to diminish the expansion in postoperative liver compound dimensions, in spite of the fact that the clinical importance of this remaining parts obscure (Nishiyama et al 2004). The customary way to deal with neuromuscular bar has been to utilize specialists that don't rely upon hepatic digestion (for example atracurium/cisatracurium), anyway both rocuronium and vecuronium (which are hepatically utilized) are generally utilized by and by (Stümphe et al, 2009).

There is the potential for enormous intraoperative discharge amid liver resection and the analgesic method must make arrangements both for limiting the danger of this happening and treating it should it emerge. Expansive bore venous access must be verified and notwithstanding fundamental observing intrusive blood vessel and focal venous weight checking considers nearer haemodynamic control and blood gas investigation. Patients with cardiovascular illness may profit by heart yield observing, for example, the oesophageal doppler (Deltex restorative, Chichester, UK) or heartbeat form examination screens, for example, LiDCOrapid® (Lidco, Cambridge, UK) or PICCO® (Philips, UK). These might be particularly valuable to screen the cardiovascular changes related with Pringle's move and furthermore control intravenous liquid substitution once the resection is finished.

Figure 1 . Organ response to hepatic dysfunction.

Amid resection of liver parenchyma the primary wellspring of draining is from the valveless hepatic veins. Hepatic venous weight is reliant on focal venous weight (CVP) and it has been exhibited that by keeping up a low intraoperative CVP it is conceivable to lessen blood misfortune (Johnson et al, 1998; Jones et al, 1998). Jones and associates announced that the normal blood misfortune was 200 ml if CVP was <6 cm H₂O, however 1000 ml if CVP was >6 cm H₂O. Furthermore the transfusion rate expanded from 5% to 48%. Systems used to keep up a low CVP can incorporate; setting the patient in the invert --trendelenburg position (head---up); shirking of positive end---expiratory weight (PEEP); insignificant intraoperative

liquid organization; utilization of diuretic operators for example furosemide; utilization of vasodilators for example glyceryl trinitrate (GTN); utilization of epidural absense of pain (Stümphe et al, 2009). Be that as it may, keeping up a low CVP opens the patient to hypovolaemia and the potential for lacking organ perfusion with consequent brokenness. There is likewise the low, yet possibly genuine danger of air embolism with air being entrained into the hepatic venules: evaluated rate of 0.1% in one investigation (Allen and Jarnagin, 2003). A few investigations report a 3% danger of lasting kidney brokenness following significant liver resection utilizing a low CVP method (Lentschener and Ozier, 2002). Nonetheless, a review examination of 496 patients in 1998 did not discover any instances of renal disappointment straightforwardly owing to this methodology (Melendez et al, 1998). Patients with preoperative cirrhosis endure a decrease in renal perfusion weight ineffectively and additional consideration must be taken to keep up perfusion weight so as to safeguard renal capacity (Redai et al, 2004).

Not all focuses utilize a low CVP strategy and there have been contemplates that have detailed low mean blood misfortune free of CVP. A survey of 30 living contributors who experienced a privilege or left hemi---hepatectomy for transplantation, announced a mean blood loss of 72±58.9 ml with a mean CVP of 7±2 cmH2O (Chen et al, 2000). Keeping up a low CVP might be alluring however it isn't fundamental to lessen intraoperative dying, fastidious careful system is similarly significant.

Table 1 Risk factors for post-resection liver failure (Hammond et al, 2011)

Operative Factors	Patient Factors
Extent of resection (> 4 segments)	Parenchymal disease: cirrhosis, non- alcoholic fatty liver disease, chemotherapy- induced liver injury (steatohepatitis and sinusoidal injury) and cholestasis
Use of intraoperative vascular occlusive techniques	Age > 65 yrs
Ex vivo hepatic resection and re--- implantation	Diabetes mellitus
Excessive blood loss and transfusion	Malnutrition
Vascular or biliary reconstruction	Male sex

Table 2 Child-Turcotte-Pugh scoring system.

Measure	1 point	2 points	3 points
---------	---------	----------	----------

Total bilirubin (μmol.L⁻¹)	<34	34 -- 50	>50
Serum albumin (g.L⁻¹)	>35	28 -- 35	<28
INR	<1.7	1.7 –2.3	>2.3
Ascites	None	Small or diuretic-controlled	Tense
Hepatic	None	Grade I -- II	Grade III – IV

Elements of an enhanced recovery programme

Although the principle in enhanced recovery is that all elements of the pathway are supported by evidence to show their benefits, in actuality some elements have stronger evidence than others. Certain elements have been shown to be clearly beneficial, whereas some others are included because the consensus view of the ERAS group is that they make good common sense even if strong evidence to support them does not exist. A further caveat is that, as mentioned, the ERAS group is principally concerned with colorectal surgery and the evidence for these elements comes from work done in patients in this area.

Figure 2 Elements of an enhanced recovery programme

Figure 3 The approach to percutaneous LB. LB =liver biopsy.

Conclusion

We enumerate the broad range of anesthetic considerations that affect the outcome of patients undergoing laparoscopic liver resection. Key elements for excellent outcomes after laparoscopic liver resection are careful patient selection and risk stratification, appropriate monitoring, techniques to reduce blood loss and transfusion, and active recovery management. Although some of these key elements are the same for open liver operation, there are specific anesthetic considerations of which both the surgical and anesthesia teams must be aware to achieve optimal patient outcomes after laparoscopic liver resection. While unique advantages of laparoscopic liver resection typically include decreased intraoperative bleeding, transfusion requirements, and a lower incidence of postoperative ascites, specific challenges include management of the complicated interplay between low-volume anesthesia and increased intraabdominal pressure due to pneumoperitoneum, with additional considerations regarding circulatory support to treat acute blood loss with need for emergent conversion in some cases..

References

1. Buell JF, Thomas MJ, Doty TC, et al. An initial experience and evolution of laparoscopic hepatic resectional surgery. *Surgery* 2004; 136:804.
2. Cherqui D, Husson E, Hammoud R, et al. Laparoscopic liver resections: a feasibility study in 30 patients. *Ann Surg* 2000; 232:753.

3. Buell JF, Cherqui D, Geller DA, et al. The international position on laparoscopic liver surgery: The Louisville Statement, 2008. *Ann Surg* 2009; 250:825.
4. Dimick JB, Wainess RM, Cowan JA, et al. National trends in the use and outcomes of hepatic resection. *J Am Coll Surg* 2004; 199:31.
5. Ciria R, Cherqui D, Geller DA, et al. Comparative Short-term Benefits of Laparoscopic Liver Resection: 9000 Cases and Climbing. *Ann Surg* 2016; 263:761.
6. Wakabayashi G, Cherqui D, Geller DA, et al. Recommendations for laparoscopic liver resection: a report from the second international consensus conference held in Morioka. *Ann Surg* 2015; 261:619.
7. He J, Amini N, Spolverato G, et al. National trends with a laparoscopic liver resection: results from a population-based analysis. *HPB (Oxford)* 2015; 17:919.
8. Farges O, Goutte N, Dokmak S, et al. How surgical technology translates into practice: the model of laparoscopic liver resections performed in France. *Ann Surg* 2014; 260:916.
9. Alkhalili E, Berber E. Laparoscopic liver resection for malignancy: a review of the literature. *World J Gastroenterol* 2014; 20:13599.
10. Aldrighetti L, Guzzetti E, Pulitanò C, et al. Case-matched analysis of totally laparoscopic versus open liver resection for HCC: short and middle term results. *J Surg Oncol* 2010; 102:82.
11. Koffron AJ, Auffenberg G, Kung R, Abecassis M. Evaluation of 300 minimally invasive liver resections at a single institution: less is more. *Ann Surg* 2007; 246:385.
12. Cannon RM, Scoggins CR, Callender GG, et al. Laparoscopic versus open resection of hepatic colorectal metastases. *Surgery* 2012; 152:567.
13. Schiffman SC, Kim KH, Tsung A, et al. Laparoscopic versus open liver resection for metastatic colorectal cancer: a metaanalysis of 610 patients. *Surgery* 2015; 157:211.
14. Cherqui D. Evolution of laparoscopic liver resection. *Br J Surg* 2016; 103:1405.
15. Fuks D, Nomi T, Ogiso S, et al. Laparoscopic two-stage hepatectomy for bilobar colorectal liver metastases. *Br J Surg* 2015; 102:1684.
16. Nguyen KT, Marsh JW, Tsung A, et al. Comparative benefits of laparoscopic vs open hepatic resection: a critical appraisal. *Arch Surg* 2011; 146:348.
17. Yoon YS, Han HS, Cho JY, et al. Is Laparoscopy Contraindicated for Gallbladder Cancer? A 10-Year Prospective Cohort Study. *J Am Coll Surg* 2015; 221:847.
18. Kandil E, Noureldine SI, Koffron A, et al. Outcomes of laparoscopic and open resection for neuroendocrine liver metastases. *Surgery* 2012; 152:1225.

19. Kim Y, Amini N, He J, et al. National trends in the use of surgery for benign hepatic tumors in the United States. *Surgery* 2015; 157:1055.
20. Dokmak S, Raut V, Aussilhou B, et al. Laparoscopic left lateral resection is the gold standard for benign liver lesions: a case-control study. *HPB (Oxford)* 2014; 16:183.
21. Mezhir JJ, Fourman LT, Do RK, et al. Changes in the management of benign liver tumours: an analysis of 285 patients. *HPB (Oxford)* 2013; 15:156.
22. Akyuz M, Yazici P, Yigitbas H, et al. Oncologic results of laparoscopic liver resection for malignant liver tumors. *J Surg Oncol* 2016; 113:127.
23. Yoon YS, Han HS, Cho JY, et al. Laparoscopic liver resection for centrally located tumors close to the hilum, major hepatic veins, or inferior vena cava. *Surgery* 2013; 153:502.
24. Egger ME, Gottumukkala V, Wilks JA, et al. Anesthetic and operative considerations for laparoscopic liver resection. *Surgery* 2017; 161:1191.
25. Di Fabio F, Barkhatov L, Bonadio I, et al. The impact of laparoscopic versus open colorectal cancer surgery on subsequent laparoscopic resection of liver metastases: A multicenter study. *Surgery* 2015; 157:1046.
26. Cauchy F, Fuks D, Nomi T, et al. Risk factors and consequences of conversion in laparoscopic major liver resection. *Br J Surg* 2015; 102:785.
27. Cipriani F, Shelat VG, Rawashdeh M, et al. Laparoscopic Parenchymal-Sparing Resections for Nonperipheral Liver Lesions, the Diamond Technique: Technical Aspects, Clinical Outcomes, and Oncologic Efficiency. *J Am Coll Surg* 2015; 221:265.
28. Vigano L, Laurent A, Tayar C, et al. The learning curve in laparoscopic liver resection: improved feasibility and reproducibility. *Ann Surg* 2009; 250:772.
29. Villani V, Bohnen JD, Torabi R, et al. "Idealized" vs. "True" learning curves: the case of laparoscopic liver resection. *HPB (Oxford)* 2016; 18:504.
30. Brown KM, Geller DA. What is the Learning Curve for Laparoscopic Major Hepatectomy? *J Gastrointest Surg* 2016; 20:1065.
31. Lin CW, Tsai TJ, Cheng TY, et al. The learning curve of laparoscopic liver resection after the Louisville statement 2008: Will it be more effective and smooth? *Surg Endosc* 2016; 30:2895.
32. Nomi T, Fuks D, Kawaguchi Y, et al. Learning curve for laparoscopic major hepatectomy. *Br J Surg* 2015; 102:796.
33. Kluger MD, Vigano L, Barroso R, Cherqui D. The learning curve in laparoscopic major liver resection. *J Hepatobiliary Pancreat Sci* 2013; 20:131.

34. Toro JP, Patel AD, Lytle NW, et al. Detecting performance variance in complex surgical procedures: analysis of a step-wise technique for laparoscopic right hepatectomy. *Am J Surg* 2015; 209:418.
35. Ogiso S, Conrad C, Araki K, et al. Laparoscopic Transabdominal With Transdiaphragmatic Access Improves Resection of Difficult Posterosuperior Liver Lesions. *Ann Surg* 2015; 262:358.
36. Machado MA, Makdissi FF, Galvão FH, Machado MC. Intrahepatic Glissonian approach for laparoscopic right segmental liver resections. *Am J Surg* 2008; 196:e38.
37. Machado MA, Surjan RC, Basseres T, et al. The laparoscopic Glissonian approach is safe and efficient when compared with standard laparoscopic liver resection: Results of an observational study over 7 years. *Surgery* 2016; 160:643.
38. Tranchart H, Di Giuro G, Lainas P, et al. Laparoscopic liver resection with selective prior vascular control. *Am J Surg* 2013; 205:8.
39. Tranchart H, O'Rourke N, Van Dam R, et al. Bleeding control during laparoscopic liver resection: a review of literature. *J Hepatobiliary Pancreat Sci* 2015; 22:371.
40. Scatton O, Brustia R, Belli G, et al. What kind of energy devices should be used for laparoscopic liver resection? Recommendations from a systematic review. *J Hepatobiliary Pancreat Sci* 2015; 22:327.

© 2019 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA . Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

